

Funded by
the European Union

GlaS - - Fuels

**Single-Atom
Photocatalysts
Enhanced by a
Self-Powered
Photonic Glass
Reactor to Produce
Advanced Biofuels**

The Project

GlaS-A-Fuels aims to transform bio-ethanol into advanced biofuels like Butanol (BuOH), heavier alcohols and hydrogen (H₂), using recyclable and cooperative catalysts from earth-abundant elements.

The concept is based on the engineering of a photonic glass reactor, self-powered by a thermoelectric module, that traps and tunes light and enhances the effectiveness of photo-amplified single-atom catalysts.

**Waste
Biomass**

**Bioethanol
Production**

**Photo-amplified
single-atom catalysts**

**Advanced Biofuels C4+
Alcohols, and H₂**

Technology

Incorporation of functional thermoelectric composite polymers and highly luminescent perovskite films in the photonic glass reactor

Use of femtosecond (fs) laser-processing for the formation of patterns on the glass surfaces to enhance the optical and emission properties of the photonic glass reactor

Engineering of single-atom catalysts with photo-triggered functions for 2G biofuels

Key Innovations

**Method for integrating
PNCs-PL and
thermoelectric (TE)
composite materials
into inorganic glasses**

**Introduction of
Photo-active Single
Atom Catalysts
(Photo-SACs)**

**Creation of
polymer-based
thermoelectric
materials**

**Implementation of
an intelligent control
system**

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Tangible Impact

SOCIAL

Increased biofuel production with a mission to expand renewable energy

ENVIRONMENTAL

Reduction in CO2 emissions

Use of bioethanol produced from bio-waste

ECONOMIC

Introduction of biobutanol as a cutting-edge transportation biofuel

Alternative pathway for green hydrogen production

Boost in bioethanol demand

Job growth in the biofuels industry

5 Partners | 4 Countries

2.99M Budget | 42 Months

 @glasafuels

 GlaS-A-Fuels Project

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